

Use of ICT in Libraries

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Abstract:

Paper deals with application of ICT tools and techniques in academic libraries in present scenario. The new information technologies can potentially support a number of traditional and non-traditional library services. Because of ICT developments, the library environment has changed from a traditional model to a modern library. The structure, management, and retrieval of information have also changed in the ICT era. The impact of the Web-based learning and teaching environment has affected all facets of library and information services in academic libraries, providing library professionals with new opportunities and challenges for participating in the knowledge-based society, including electronic and multimedia publishing, Internet-based information services, global networking, Web-based digital resources, etc.

Keywords - ICT, Library services

Introduction:

The use of computers has been steadily increasing in science and technology since 2nd world war. Internet access is one of the greatest technological advancement being experienced in this 21st century. To render best services to users. Libraries and Library professional are using various type of technologies to provide the updated and desired information, computing communication, storage and retrieval are the areas of continues development and remodeling to dissemination information and to meet users satisfaction.

Academic libraries are the central part of the only institution and mend for learning, teaching and research and development process. ICT act as primary roots of Banyan tree with many branches covering creation, communication, distribution and administration which are pillared by prop roots like Internet, Telephones, Mobiles. Television, Radio, Audio, Visual, sate light communication hardware, software, etc. In a changing environment, most of the library services are ICT based and it is important for library professionals to be well informed and updated regarding developments in ICT. The development and changes in the ICT have changed the user's expectations from the academic libraries in different ways.

Library and information professionals are facing various issues like -

1. The transition from paper to electronic media as the dominant form of information dissemination, storage and retrieval,
2. Increasing demand for accountability along with focus on customer services, performance measurement, bench marking and continuous improvement.
3. Introduction of new forms of work organization such as work teams, job sharing, outsourcing, re-engineering etc.

ICT and Library:

There has been rapid development in the field of information technology. The three important elements in information technology are computer,

communication technology and internet. Many libraries have been computerized to some extent. The modern librarians have trying to get acquainted and familiar with the new technology which has changed the face and interface of library.

Library cannot depend on printed books alone, but it has to make use of computer technology also. The information atmosphere around the world is changing every minute and growing at a tremendous speed due to the emergence of the web based Information and Communication Technologies, globalization of networks and Internet. Acquiring and providing access to electronic knowledge resources require library professional to change their role from traditional librarian to information scientist by learning and applying new skills to understand the evolving technologies to manage and provide quality on line information service to the patrons of the knowledge society. Almost all the educational institutions, organizations, universities and academic associations have created their websites with the digital repositories on internet the global networked environment has paved the way and opportunity to e literacy.

Impact of ICT on Library services:

Use of ICT has changed the fundamental roles, paradigms and organizational culture of libraries and librarians. ICT offering a vast information source and new modes of information delivery. There is a continuing evolution of the roles and functions of libraries and librarians, which appear parallel the growth of acceptance of ICT by library professionals.

The library services are basically same in the traditional and electronic libraries. The web sites for libraries are essential in today's environment. Web site supports library services in a better way. Designing web sites is a more important task depending on the type of library. Some of the issues involved is designing the web sites for libraries, including moving form print design to web design, the use of tools available online. The Information

Technology has made its impact on the academic library in recent years in India, The library services are redefined with changing Information Technology environment. The purpose of unlimited potential of IT for modernizing the library services. The computers could make changes in the library services as an administrative tool as a resource for teaching information skill and as part of the library collection in the form of software and databases. The information technology has a positive impact on all the library and information services like library resources to varied services rendered to users.

The following list will give an idea of which various functions of libraries may take advantage from Internet and Web technologies.

1. Acquisition – Correspondence with Book seller and Publisher, Ordering, Billing, Reminder, Price verification, Online book shops e.g. Amazon
2. Classification – Dewey Online, OCLC Classify
3. Collection Development – Subscribe in print or e form, consortia
4. Cataloguing – Online Catalogues, OCLC, MARC, Metadata standards
5. Circulation – Remote login, Status check, OPAC access, Reminder to users, User request, Inter library loan
6. Resource sharing – Union Catalogue, Access, Adding downloading, Reference / Information serves, SDI,
7. Internet sources User Education – Through email, Through library blog, through web

Advantages of ICT:

1. Reduce the cost through resource sharing
2. Speed, Accuracy and reliability
3. Participate resource sharing
4. Control the information explosion through bibliographic control
5. Improve the quality of existing services
6. Effective control over entire operations
7. Avoid duplication of work
8. Facilitate wider dissemination of information products and services

Role of Librarian:

Librarian is a professionally trained person responsible for the care of a library and its contents, including the selection, processing and organization of resources and the delivery of information, instruction and loan service to meet the needs of its users. In an online environment the role of the librarian is to manage and mediate access to information that may exist only in electronic form. The environment in which librarians work is changing in terms of greater access to a range of information, greater complexity in locating, analyzing and linking information, constantly changing technology and adaptation, lack of standardization of both hardware and software,

continuous learning for users and staff, management of financial investment for technology.

Librarians are shifting their roles from facilitator to service provider and information broker supporting to the needs of user. Librarians are handling the information in digital media and using web tools and provide instant access to information available. Use of internet, web tools, portals is properly managed and shares the information which is the present and future need. Librarians educates users in searching information using modern tools and techniques and termed himself as website designer, blog builder, database manager, policy maker, business manager while negotiating with publishers and aggregators. From time to time librarian adapted the technology in the area and supported to the user needs. To cope up with the changing digital and technological environment today's librarians have to adapt new practices and competencies.

Library staff is undergoing Internet training programmes to keep pace with new technologies and to satisfy the growing complex information needs of users.

Conclusion:

The application of information technology in libraries leads to increased operational efficiency. ICT increases the productivity of library staff. New information technology facilitates access to information for library users, on the one hand, and the dissemination of information products and services created by the library, on the other. ICT has created new media and new ways of storing and transmitting information. They have brought many services to libraries to speed up their activities. Impact of ICT on all areas of library work. Technological developments lead to changes in the organization of work and the skills required change. Critical thinking, broad-based competencies, ICT skills that enable expert work, decision making, handling dynamic situations, working in teams, and communicating with others are gaining importance. The availability of networks facilitates resource sharing and high-speed communication with other libraries.

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